

PURE TENSION WITH OFF-AXIS TESTS FOR ORTHOTROPIC LAMINATES.

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SUMMARY : Orthotropic materials can be classified in four categories, two of which possessing four directions of extremum for the Young's modulus. Deformation under axial load in these directions always occur without shear. It makes possible a complete measurement of in-plane elastic constants by three pure tension tests for materials with four direction of extremum Young's modulus. This paper presents the analysis and experimental evidence for laminates.

KEYWORDS : off-axis test, tensile tests, orthotropy, elastic constants, laminates.

INTRODUCTION.

Complete determination of the mechanical properties of anisotropic materials by simple tests is still a challenge, even when limiting to elastic properties. This is mainly due to the many couplings existing in these materials, which do not allow simultaneously simple loading and simple deformation except for a limited number of cases, such as tensile tests in the directions of the symmetry axes. Generally such special cases are not enough to determine all the elastic constants. The aim of the present paper is to show that, for certain types of orthotropic materials, it is possible to design other simple tests to complete the determination of the elastic properties. More precisely, for these materials, pure tension can be obtained in the elastic range in four different directions, i.e. the two axes of symmetry and two off-axis directions (symmetrical with respect to the axes of orthotropy), all of which are directions of extremum Young's modulus and zero coupling between shear and longitudinal effects. Many composite laminates belong to this class of orthotropic materials, and consequently can be characterised completely in their elastic range by three independent tensile tests. We derive hereafter the equations and conditions of application, and give experimental evidence for such complete characterisation of orthotropic materials.

CLASSIFICATION OF PLANE ORTHOTROPIC MATERIALS.

The analysis hereafter is closely related to the tensorial nature of elastic constants (stiffnesses or compliances), so use is made of the tensorial notation, with four subscripts for the Cartesian components of these fourth order tensors. For convenience, the matching of the tensorial and usual contracted notations for compliances is reminded in Appendix 1.

As explained in Appendix 2, for an orthotropic material, the six tensorial components of the elastic compliances, in axes x, y (with axis x at the angle θ from the orthotropy axis of larger Young's modulus), can be expressed with four invariant parameters t_0, t_1, r_0, r_1 , and an integer index k , in the form :

$$(1) \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} S_{xxxx}(\theta) = t_0 + 2t_1 + (-1)^k r_0 \cos 4\theta - 4r_1 \cos 2\theta \\ S_{xxyy}(\theta) = - (-1)^k r_0 \sin 4\theta + 2r_1 \sin 2\theta \\ S_{xyxy}(\theta) = -t_0 + 2t_1 - (-1)^k r_0 \cos 4\theta \\ S_{yyxx}(\theta) = t_0 - (-1)^k r_0 \cos 4\theta \\ S_{xyyx}(\theta) = - (-1)^k r_0 \sin 4\theta + 2r_1 \sin 2\theta \\ S_{yyxy}(\theta) = t_0 + 2t_1 + (-1)^k r_0 \cos 4\theta + 4r_1 \cos 2\theta \end{array} \right.$$

From these Eqs., the following fundamental relation appears :

$$(2) \quad \frac{\partial S_{xxxx}(\theta)}{\partial \theta} = 4S_{xxyy}(\theta)$$

Consequently, the number and directions of the extremum values of Young's modulus $E(\theta)$ or its inverse $S_{xxxx}(\theta)$ are determined by the zero values of the coupling compliance $S_{xxyy}(\theta)$.

This coupling compliance, which controls the interaction between longitudinal and shear effects, can be expressed as :

$$(3) \quad S_{xxyy}(\theta) = 2r_0 \sin 2\theta \left\{ r_1/r_0 - (-1)^k \cos 2\theta \right\}$$

So, when $r_1 > r_0$, there are only two directions of extremum, which are of course the orthotropy axes, where $\sin 2\theta$ is zero.

When $r_1 \leq r_0$, the last factor in Eq.(3) can be zero too. Let :

$$(4) \quad r_1 = (-1)^k r_0 \cos 2\omega$$

with $0 \leq \omega \leq \pi/4$ for even k , and $\pi/4 \leq \omega \leq \pi/2$ for odd k . Then Eq.(3) writes :

$$(5) \quad S_{xxyy}(\theta) = 4(-1)^k r_0 \sin 2\theta \sin(\theta - \omega) \sin(\theta + \omega)$$

which shows four directions of zero coupling compliance and extremum Young's modulus, at relative angles equal to $0^\circ, 90^\circ$, and $\pm \omega$.

Consequently, orthotropic materials can be classified with respect to their compliances into four categories :

- i) odd k and $r_1 > r_0$, with only two directions of extremum values for the Young's modulus, i.e. 0° for the maximum and 90° for the minimum (relative angles),
- ii) odd k and $r_1 \leq r_0$, with four directions of extremum values, i.e. 0° for the absolute maximum, $\pm \omega$ for the two absolute minima and 90° for a local minimum,
- iii) even k and $r_1 > r_0$, with only two directions of extremum values for the Young's modulus, i.e. 0° for the maximum and 90° for the minimum,
- iv) even k and $r_1 \leq r_0$, with four directions of extremum values, i.e. 0° for a local minimum, $\pm \omega$ for the two absolute maxima and 90° for the absolute minimum.

For case ii) (odd k), the polar curve representing the Young's modulus with the direction is cross-shaped, with its longer branches along the 0° direction, while for case iv) (even k), this curve is bone-shaped, with its major extensions along the $\pm \omega$ directions. Further, for both cases, it can be shown that the shear modulus in the 0° (or 90°) direction is related to the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio in the $+\omega$ (or $-\omega$) direction, according to the formula :

$$(6) \quad 2G(0) = \frac{E(\omega)}{1+\nu(\omega)}$$

which is an extension of the well-known relation between Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and shear modulus for isotropic materials.

This relation should be distinguished from the similar formula :

$$(7) \quad 2G(0) = \frac{E(\pi/4)}{1+\nu(\pi/4)}$$

which holds for any orthotropic material, but does not relate properties in directions of simple tests.

Such theoretical classification is really meaningful. It can be checked easily from published data for crystal elastic constants [1] that different cases do exist for crystals. Further, for laminates, for which elastic properties can be tailored by control of the stacking sequence, all types can be obtained. Using the classical laminated plate theory and varying the basic laminas and the stacking sequences, it is easy to predict that, for instance, laminates reinforced with unbalanced fabrics and cross-ply laminates should belong generally to the i- and ii-types, while angle-ply laminates should be generally of the iii- and iv-types.

APPLICATION TO TENSILE TESTS.

It is well-known that, in the orthotropy axes, the compliance matrix has the following form :

$$(8) \quad \begin{pmatrix} S_{1111} & S_{1122} & 0 \\ S_{1122} & S_{2222} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 4S_{1212} \end{pmatrix}$$

which shows that unidirectional load along any orthotropy axis produces longitudinal and transverse strains, without shear deformation.

Now let us consider Cartesian axes in the off-axis direction ω of extremum Young's modulus and its orthogonal direction ζ . In these axes, it results from Eq.(2) that the coupling compliance $S_{\omega\omega\omega\zeta}$, proportional to the derivative of the longitudinal compliance $S_{\omega\omega\omega\omega}$, is zero. So the compliance matrix gets the special form :

$$(9) \quad \begin{pmatrix} S_{\omega\omega\omega\omega} & S_{\omega\omega\zeta\zeta} & 0 \\ S_{\omega\omega\zeta\zeta} & S_{\zeta\zeta\zeta\zeta} & 2S_{\omega\zeta\zeta\zeta} \\ 0 & 2S_{\omega\zeta\zeta\zeta} & 4S_{\omega\zeta\omega\zeta} \end{pmatrix}$$

Comparison between Eqs. (8) and (9) shows that stress-strain behaviour in these axes is not so simple than in the orthotropy axes. The non-zero compliance $S_{\omega\zeta\zeta\zeta}$ induces coupling between shear and extension in the ζ direction. However, no coupling occurs for unidirectional load in the ω direction. In other words, **pure tension occurs** for loading in the direction of extremum Young's modulus.

It results that four pure tension tests can be applied to orthotropic materials falling into categories ii and iv described in the previous section, in the four different directions of maximum or minimum Young's modulus (0° , 90° and $\pm\omega$). Each test can lead to two strain measurements in the longitudinal and transverse directions, providing eight values of the Young's moduli and the Poisson's ratios in the corresponding directions. Of course, all these values are not independent. Specially, it is obvious that measurements at $+\omega$ and $-\omega$ should give the same results for Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios, and it is well known that the Poisson's ratios at 0° and 90° satisfy a reciprocity relation. However, four independent quantities can be extracted from the measurements, leading to a complete characterisation of the elastic properties of the materials, with the Young's moduli at 0° and 90° , the Poisson's ratio at 0° and the shear modulus at 0° . According to Eq.(6), the shear modulus can be obtained simply by combining strain measurements for tension in the ω direction. Other measurements can be discarded, or used to check the relations occurring between non independent quantities, or also incorporated with the others in an optimisation process for better determination of elastic constants, as described in Ref.[2]. Finally, although not strictly necessary, measurements of shear strain during the off-axis tension tests could be done, in order to check that shear is null, so to confirm the state of pure tension.

EXPERIMENTAL IMPLEMENTATION.

An experimental research was conducted on various laminates to illustrate this off-axis pure tension test. We manufactured glass-epoxy and carbon-epoxy laminates from prepregs by hot-pressing. Specimens were cut in the 0° , 90° and ω directions and equipped with three-directional rosettes on both faces (gauges at 0° , 45° , and 90° in the specimen axes). The classical laminated plate theory was used to predict the value of the off-axis angle ω .

For the off-axis test, we actually observed that the shear strain in the specimen axes (obtained by combining conveniently the signals of the three gauges) was zero with an excellent precision all along the elastic range, demonstrating a pure tension, as in the orthotropy directions.

From these three pure tension tests, we got enough independent measurements to determine completely the elastic properties of laminates. We measured the Young's moduli and the

Poisson's ratio directly from the signals of the 0° and 90° gauges with the two classical tension tests in the orthotropy directions, and the shear modulus by combining the signals of the 0° and 90° gauges in the off-axis pure tension test, in accordance with Eq.(6). From these in-plane engineering constants, we also computed compliances and stiffnesses.

Table 1 gives results obtained for a 17-ply carbon-epoxy laminate with the following antisymmetrical stacking sequence (angles in degrees, from the bottom to the top) :

$$[- 30_2 / 90 / 30_5 / 90 / - 30_5 / 90 / 30_2] .$$

Experimental values are followed by their standard deviation in brackets. The Young's and shear moduli are in GPa. Predictions obtained from the classical laminated plate theory (CLPT) with experimental data for the lamina properties are also presented for comparison purpose. The selected off-axis angle ω , as obtained by the classical laminated plate theory, was 28°.

Table 1.

	E_1	E_2	ν_{12}	G_{12}
Experiment	55.7 (2.18)	34.2 (1.37)	.55 (.008)	23.5 (.75)
CLPT	56.76	32.53	.537	23.05

COMMENTS AND CONCLUSION.

We have shown, by analysis and experiment, that it is possible, for certain types of orthotropic laminates, to determine completely the in-plane elastic properties (membrane stiffnesses, compliances and engineering constants) from a total of three pure tension tests (an off-axis test in a special direction and the two classical tension tests in the axes of symmetry).

The present work can receive several interesting extensions.

First, we have shown in another work that similar theory and experiment apply to bending tests for some types of laminates orthotropic in flexure, leading to a complete determination of their bending stiffnesses.

Further, the basic relation between the derivative of the inverse of the Young's modulus and the coupling compliance is not limited to orthotropy. In fact it is valid for complete anisotropy, and anisotropic materials can be classified in four categories with respect to their compliances, with two or four directions of extremum Young's moduli. As in the orthotropic case, pure tension tests can be achieved in these directions.

Finally, in the off-axis tensile tests, we observed that the shear strains remained very small beyond the limit of linearity, thus suggesting that this off-axis test might be extended in the non-elastic range. However, this needs further experimental confirmation, which is presently in progress.

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APPENDIX 1.

The relation between the so-called contracted notation and the tensorial notation for the fourth order compliance tensor introduces factors 2 and 4, and is given in matrix form as :

$$(A-1) \quad \begin{pmatrix} S_{1111} & S_{1122} & 2S_{1112} \\ S_{1122} & S_{2222} & 2S_{1222} \\ 2S_{1112} & 2S_{1222} & 4S_{1212} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{16} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{26} \\ S_{16} & S_{26} & S_{66} \end{pmatrix}$$

Further, for orthotropic materials, in the symmetry axes, the engineering constants and the components of the compliance tensor are related by :

$$(A-2) \quad \begin{pmatrix} S_{1111} & S_{1122} & 0 \\ S_{1122} & S_{2222} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 4S_{1212} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{21}/E_2 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 1/E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{pmatrix}$$

Beware of different definitions that may be found for Poisson's ratios (compare [3], [4], [5]).

APPENDIX 2.

The polar description of anisotropy was introduced in a general form by Verchery [6], [7]. It represents any plane tensor with scalars, moduli (which are positive) and polar angles, generalising known concepts such as modulus and angle for a vector, Mohr's circle construction for second order symmetrical tensors, Tsai's circles for fourth order elasticity tensors [4], [5].

With this polar representation, for a completely anisotropic material, the six Cartesian components of the elastic compliances are expressed in any Cartesian axes x_1 and x_2 with two scalars t_0, t_1 , two moduli r_1, r_0 , and two polar angles φ_0, φ_1 , as :

$$(A-3) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} S_{1111} = t_0 + 2t_1 + r_0 \cos 4\varphi_0 + 4r_1 \cos 2\varphi_1 \\ S_{1112} = r_0 \sin 4\varphi_0 + 2r_1 \sin 2\varphi_1 \\ S_{1122} = -t_0 + 2t_1 - r_0 \cos 4\varphi_0 \\ S_{1212} = t_0 - r_0 \cos 4\varphi_0 \\ S_{1222} = -r_0 \sin 4\varphi_0 + 2r_1 \sin 2\varphi_1 \\ S_{2222} = t_0 + 2t_1 + r_0 \cos 4\varphi_0 - 4r_1 \cos 2\varphi_1 \end{array} \right.$$

Whereas the transformation relations, when the axes are rotated by an angle θ , are rather cumbersome for the Cartesian components, they get a very simple form for these polar parameters. Namely, the polar angles are decreased by this same angle θ , while the scalars and the moduli are invariant, as well as the difference between the polar angles.

Coming back to the Cartesian components gives in the new axes x and y (for general anisotropy and arbitrary reference axes x_1 and x_2):

$$(A-4) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} S_{xxxx} = t_0 + 2t_1 + r_0 \cos 4(\varphi_0 - \theta) + 4r_1 \cos 2(\varphi_1 - \theta) \\ S_{xxyy} = r_0 \sin 4(\varphi_0 - \theta) + 2r_1 \sin 2(\varphi_1 - \theta) \\ S_{xyxy} = -t_0 + 2t_1 - r_0 \cos 4(\varphi_0 - \theta) \\ S_{xyyy} = t_0 - r_0 \cos 4(\varphi_0 - \theta) \\ S_{yyyy} = -r_0 \sin 4(\varphi_0 - \theta) + 2r_1 \sin 2(\varphi_1 - \theta) \\ S_{yyyy} = t_0 + 2t_1 + r_0 \cos 4(\varphi_0 - \theta) - 4r_1 \cos 2(\varphi_1 - \theta) \end{array} \right.$$

It can be shown that orthotropy is obtained when the following invariant relation holds :

$$(A-5) \quad \varphi_0 - \varphi_1 = k \pi/4$$

where k is an integer and the orthotropy axes are at angles φ_1 and $\varphi_1 + \pi/2$.

From Eqs.(A-3), it appears that there are only two distinct cases, i.e. for even and for odd values of k . However, these two cases can be analysed simultaneously.

Finally, it is convenient in the orthotropic case to choose the reference axes so that $\varphi_1 = \pi/2$.

Consequently the axes x_1 and x_2 are the orthotropy directions, with the Young's modulus being larger along the first axis than in the second ($E_1 > E_2$, or conversely $S_{1111} < S_{2222}$).

Then, with θ being the relative angle (from the x_1 axis to the current x axis of the rotated frame), the Cartesian components of the compliance in axes x and y write as in Eq.(1).